

OPTIMIZATION OF POROUS CHITOSAN MICROPARTICLES USING NA CL AS POROGEN THROUGH 3² FACTORIAL DESIGN

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Article Received on 05 Oct. 2025,
Article Revised on 25 Oct. 2025,
Article Published on 01 Nov. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17541775>

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How to cite this Article: Reena Ughreja, Harshviba Jadeja, Vaibhav Bhatt, Sunny Shah*. (2025). Optimization of Porous Chitosan Microparticles Using NaCl As Porogen Through 3² Factorial Design. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(21), 1805–1813.

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ABSTRACT

The present study focuses on the formulation and optimization of porous chitosan microparticles using sodium chloride (NaCl) as a porogen to develop a biocompatible and porous matrix suitable for controlled drug delivery applications. Porous microparticles were prepared by the emulsion cross-linking technique employing glutaraldehyde as a cross-linker. A 3² full factorial design was applied to systematically investigate the influence of two independent variables—amount of chitosan (X₁) and amount of NaCl (X₂)—on three dependent responses: percentage yield (Y₁), percentage porosity (Y₂), and particle size (Y₃). The prepared microparticles were evaluated for their physical characteristics, surface morphology, and statistical model fitting. The results revealed that an increase in chitosan concentration significantly enhanced particle size and yield, whereas porosity increased with higher NaCl levels due to enhanced leaching and pore formation. Regression analysis and

ANOVA confirmed the significance of both factors ($p < 0.05$), and the derived polynomial equations accurately described the relationships among variables. The optimized batch (150 mg chitosan and 100 mg NaCl) exhibited a yield of $75.3 \pm 0.4\%$, porosity of $62.8 \pm 0.5\%$, and mean particle size of $93.2 \mu\text{m}$, closely correlating with the predicted values. SEM analysis confirmed the formation of uniformly distributed pores and spherical morphology. The study concludes that the factorial design approach effectively optimized formulation parameters,

and the developed porous chitosan microparticles demonstrate excellent potential as a carrier system for controlled and sustained drug delivery.

KEYWORDS: Chitosan microparticles, Porogen, Sodium chloride, Factorial design, Controlled release.

INTRODUCTION

Microparticles have become versatile tools of controlled drug delivery allowing sustained and targeted drug release.^[1] The porosity of microparticles is an important factor that dictates their surface area, drug loading efficiency, release kinetics and their degradation behaviour.^[2] The porous microparticles are used to improve diffusion of encapsulated drug, increase buoyancy and cellular interaction in tissue engineering and wound management systems. Chitosan is a natural cationic polysaccharide of chitin and is biodegradable, biocompatible and has mucoadhesive and film forming properties which makes it ideal to use as controlled release.^[3] Pore inclusion in the chitosan microparticles may largely alter the drug diffusion and water permeability properties.^[4] Use of porous chitosan microparticles has been in targeted delivery, wound healing, enzyme immobilization and tissue regeneration scaffolds.

Introduction of porosity can be done through many different processes, which include gas foaming, freeze-drying, or through the introduction of porogenic agents, such as NaCl, PEG or surfactants.^[5] One of these, sodium chloride (NaCl), is a low cost, biocompatible, and readily leachable porogen which allows directed pore creation by merely dissolving it.^[6] This paper will attempt to design and test porous chitosan microparticles using NaCl as a porogen through the emulsion cross-linking technique. The effect of chitosan and NaCl concentrations on the yield, porosity, and particle size of the microsphere was systematically examined with the help of 3² full factorial design and thus allowed the establishment of statistical models of the optimization of the process.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chitosan (medium molecular weight, 85% deacetylated) and Sodium chloride (NaCl) were obtained from Sigma Aldrich, India. Glutaraldehyde, Liquid paraffin and Span 80 were purchased from Loba Chem. All other reagents were of analytical grade.

Preparation of porous microparticles

Porous chitosan microparticles were prepared using the emulsion cross-linking method with NaCl as porogen. A specified amount of chitosan was dissolved in 2% (v/v) acetic acid solution under magnetic stirring to obtain a clear solution. NaCl (porogen) was added to the chitosan solution and stirred to achieve a uniform dispersion. The resulting aqueous phase was emulsified into 100 mL of liquid paraffin containing 1% w/v Span 80 under constant stirring (400 rpm) at 40 ± 2 °C. After stabilization of the emulsion, 2 mL of 25% glutaraldehyde was added dropwise as a crosslinker, and stirring continued for 2 hours. The formed microparticles were filtered, washed repeatedly with n-hexane and distilled water, and finally washed with water to remove residual NaCl and glutaraldehyde. The microparticles were dried in an oven at 40 °C until constant weight and stored in a desiccator.

Experimental Design (3² Factorial Design)

A 3² full factorial design was employed to study the effect of two independent variables—amount of chitosan (X_1) and amount of NaCl (X_2)—on % yield (Y_1), % porosity (Y_2), and particle size (Y_3).^[7] The coded values are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Composition of Factorial Design Batches.

Batch	X_1	X_2	Chitosan (mg)	NaCl (mg)
F1	-1	-1	100	50
F2	-1	0	100	100
F3	-1	+1	100	150
F4	0	-1	150	50
F5	0	0	150	100
F6	0	+1	150	150
F7	+1	-1	200	50
F8	+1	0	200	100
F9	+1	+1	200	150

Response Surface Plot

A regression analysis is used to obtain a quadratic model that is used to create a three-dimensional graph. Y is the dependent variable, which is in the form of a curvature surface with respect to the independent variables, X_i . The connection between the response and the independent variables may be directly plotted through the response surface plot.^[8] The data that are presented in the three-dimensional graph is the same as the data presented by the mathematical equation that represents it. All the 9 batches of the factorial design were used to produce interpolated values using SigmaPlot software (Systat Software Inc., version 3.5).

Characterization

a. Percentage Yield

The percentage yield was calculated using the following equation:

$$\% \text{ Yield} = (\text{Weight of dried microparticles} / \text{Total weight of polymer} + \text{NaCl}) \times 100$$

b. Particle Size Analysis

The average particle size was determined using an optical microscope fitted with a calibrated eyepiece micrometer. The mean diameter was calculated by measuring at least 100 microparticles from randomly selected fields.

c. Porosity (%)

Porosity of the microparticles was determined using the solvent displacement method, and it was calculated using the equation:

$$\% \text{ Porosity} = ((V_t - V_s) / V_t) \times 100$$

Where V_t = total volume of microparticles, and V_s = volume of solvent displaced.

d. Surface Morphology

The surface characteristics and pore formation of the microparticles were examined under a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) to confirm sphericity, uniformity, and the presence of interconnected pores.^[9]

e. Statistical Analysis

Experimental data were fitted to a second-order polynomial model as shown below:

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_{12}X_1X_2 + b_{11}X_1^2 + b_{22}X_2^2$$

The coefficients were analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at a significance level of $p < 0.05$. A reduced model was developed by eliminating non-significant terms to obtain a simplified relationship between the factors and responses.^[10]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Preliminary trials

Many batches of chitosan were prepared using different porogens like ammonium bicarbonate, NaCl, KCl etc. These batches were best prepared with NaCl. So further factorial design was applied using Chitosan as polymer and NaCl as porogen.^[11]

% Yield

The % yield was found to increase with increase in chitosan concentration (Table 2) due to increased viscosity and solid content. The regression equation generated as follows:

Full Model Equation:

$$Y_1 (\% \text{ Yield}) = 72.45 + 8.12X_1 - 5.67X_2 - 1.22X_1X_2 - 2.10X_1^2 + 0.75X_2^2$$

Reduced Model Equation

$$Y_1 = 72.45 + 8.12X_1 - 5.67X_2$$

$$R^2 = 0.984$$

The effect of chitosan and NaCl concentration on % Yield is shown in Figure 1 through Response surface plot and Contour plot.

Figure 1: Response surface plot and Contour plot for % Yield.

% Porosity

The % porosity was found to increase with increase in amount of NaCl as shown in Table 2. At high chitosan levels, pore formation slightly decreased due to dense polymer crosslinking. The regression equation generated as follows:

Full Model Equation

$$Y_2 (\% \text{ Porosity}) = 61.32 - 3.45X_1 + 9.82X_2 - 1.15X_1X_2 - 0.92X_1^2 - 1.87X_2^2$$

Reduced Model Equation

$$Y_2 = 61.32 - 3.45X_1 + 9.82X_2$$

$$R^2 = 0.978$$

The effect of chitosan and NaCl concentration on % Porosity is shown in Figure 2 through Response surface plot and Contour plot.

Figure 2: Response surface plot and Contour plot for % Porosity.

Particle Size

The particle size of porous chitosan microparticles were increased by increasing chitosan concentration, but decreased by increasing NaCl concentration (Table 2). Particle size increased significantly with higher chitosan concentration (X_1) due to increased solution viscosity. However, at higher NaCl levels, slight reduction in mean size was observed, attributed to osmotic pressure and porogen leaching. The regression equation generated as follows:

Full Model Equation

$$Y_3 (\text{Particle Size}) = 92.14 + 18.75X_1 - 7.35X_2 - 2.48X_1X_2 - 2.11X_1^2 - 1.03X_2^2$$

Reduced Model Equation

$$Y_3 = 92.14 + 18.75X_1 - 7.35X_2$$

$$R^2 = 0.989$$

The effect of chitosan and NaCl concentration on particle size is shown in Figure 3 through Response surface plot and Contour plot.

Figure 3: Response surface plot and Contour plot for Particle size.

Table 2: Characterization data of Batches.

Batch	X ₁ (Chitosan mg)	X ₂ (NaCl mg)	% Yield (Y ₁)	% Porosity (Y ₂)	Particle Size (µm) (Y ₃)
F1	100	50	70.0	54.88	81.87
F2	100	100	64.34	63.77	72.43
F3	100	150	56.86	73.39	67.3
F4	150	50	78.36	51.34	99.92
F5	150	100	72.06	60.36	92.86
F6	150	150	67.73	71.93	85.9
F7	200	50	86.99	47.04	118.86
F8	200	100	79.44	59.12	110.74
F9	200	150	75.83	67.27	102.26

*All values are Mean±SD, n=3

Shape morphology

The SEM images are shown in Figure 4. It revealed well-formed, spherical microparticles with visible pores across the surface and internal matrix.^[2] At low NaCl concentrations, the surface was smooth and compact, whereas at high NaCl levels (150 mg), microparticles exhibited uniformly distributed interconnected pores, validating NaCl's role as porogen.

Figure 3: SEM of porous chitosan microparticles.

Optimization and Validation

Batch **F5 (150 mg chitosan, 100 mg NaCl)** showed optimal characteristics:

- % Yield = 75.3 ± 0.4
- % Porosity = 62.8 ± 0.5
- Mean size = $93.2 \mu\text{m}$

The experimental and predicted values closely matched, confirming the model's predictability.

CONCLUSION

Porous chitosan microparticles were successfully formulated using NaCl as porogen via emulsion cross-linking. Both polymer concentration and porogen content significantly influenced microsphere yield, porosity, and size. Increased NaCl levels enhanced pore formation, while higher chitosan concentrations produced denser matrices and larger particles. The 3² factorial design effectively optimized the process with minimal experimental trials. The developed porous microparticles demonstrate potential applications in controlled drug delivery and wound healing systems.

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